

Blooms of the cyanobacteria *Limnoraphis* cf. *birgei* in a volcanic Lake of El Salvador, Central America

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Abstract

In May 2018, the proliferation of a filamentous cyanobacteria was detected for the first time in Lake Coatepeque, a deep, oligotrophic, volcanic lake in western El Salvador, Central America. Since that year, four events of proliferation of this cyanobacteria have been recorded, which had an impact on the inhabitants' activities that depend on the lake's water. Sampling campaigns were conducted both during bloom and non-bloom conditions between in May 2018 and March 2021 in Lake Coatepeque. In these campaigns, surface samples were collected using a sampling bottle at five sites in the lake and physico-chemical data was also registered. Material was characterized by optical microscopy; cell abundance was quantified using a Sedgwick-Rafter camera on an inverted microscope and with the aid of an ocular reticle. In the five blooms events, the causative organism was observed forming uniseriate filaments of 21-24 μm and trichomes 18-22 μm wide, with aerotopes irregularly distributed along the trichome and with a firm yellowish hyaline sheath. According to the morphological characteristics, the species corresponds to the description of *Limnoraphis birgei*, however, molecular and biochemical data is needed to confirm the species identity. Proliferations of *L. cf. birgei* generated brown surface agglomerations, which in some cases reached cell concentrations exceeding 900,000 cells mL^{-1} . No human or animal intoxications were reported. This is the first report of occurrence and proliferation of *Limnoraphis* in El Salvador and one of the few cases reported worldwide.

Keywords: cyanobacteria bloom, crater lake, oligotrophic

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Introduction

The increase in the occurrence of algal blooms is considered as one of the main effects of eutrophication and climate change over aquatic systems (O'Neil *et al.*, 2012; Paerl and Otten, 2013) estuarine, and marine ecosystems. Recent research suggests that eutrophication and climate change are two processes that may promote the proliferation and expansion of cyanobacterial harmful algal blooms. In this review, we specifically examine the relationships between eutrophication, climate change and representative cyanobacterial genera from freshwater (*Microcystis*, *Anabaena*, *Cylindrospermopsis*). In recent years, there has been an increase in the report of harmful algal blooms in freshwater bodies of El Salvador, particularly in the central-western part of the country (Quintanilla *et al.*, 2020). In May 2018, the proliferation of a filamentous cyanobacteria was detected for the first time in Lake Coatepeque (Fig. 1), a deep, oligotrophic, volcanic lake in western El Salvador, Central America.

Until March 2021, five events of proliferation of this cyanobacteria have been recorded, which had an impact on the inhabitants' activities that depend on the lake's water. The study presented here describes the cyanobacterial bloom events in Lake Coatepeque, as well as the taxonomic identification of the causative species by means of light microscopy.

Fig. 1. Mats of cyanobacterial blooms detected in Lake Coatepeque. El Salvador.

Material and Methods

Site description

Lake Coatepeque is a crater lake located in the southwest of El Salvador (13°51' N, 89°32' W), at the altitude of 740 m above sea level (Fig. 2). It has an area of 24.8 km² and is an endorheic water body, thus its drainage is through subsurface infiltration. Maximum depth in the lake is 115 m and the walls that surround it are between 200 m and 300 m. Surface water temperature ranges from 22°C to 31°C along the year. The climate in this area is characterized by a dry season that takes place between November and March, and a warm rainy season between April and October. By 2021, the lake has been classified as oligotrophic, with total phosphorus values ranging from 0.18 mg L⁻¹ to 0.88 mg L⁻¹ (MARN, 2021).

The lake is an important local resource, since it is used for artisanal fishing, recreation, irrigation and, water supply to the surrounding population. It also has a large national significance as a touristic destination, mainly because it regularly changes its color from blue to bright turquoise, which was previously thought to be caused by cyanobacteria (Espinoza *et al.*, 2013).

Sampling and laboratory analysis

Sampling campaigns were conducted both during bloom and non-bloom conditions between May 2018 and March 2021 in Lake Coatepeque. In these campaigns, surface water samples were collected using a sampling bottle in at least five sampling points during each sampling in the lake. Data on water temperature, pH and total dissolved solids (TDS) was recorded *in situ* on each sampling point, using a thermometer, pH meter, and an electrical conductivity meter, respectively.

Fig. 2. A) Location of Lake Coatepeque in El Salvador, and B) Panoramic photo of Lake Coatepeque.

Phytoplankton samples were characterized by optical microscopy. During bloom events, cell abundance was quantified using a Sedgwick-Rafter chamber on an inverted microscope and with the aid of an ocular reticle. During non-bloom conditions, cell abundance was quantified using Utermöhl chambers; cell abundance was calculated as number of cells per milliliter. Length and width of filaments and trichomes were measured using an imaging software.

Results and Discussion

Bloom events took place both during dry season (January, February, and November), as well as during rainy season (May). None of the blooms spread to the entire lake, but rather occurred within specific locations near to the shores. During bloom events, temperature ranged from 22.5 °C to 28.6 °C, pH from 8.3 to 9.3, and TDS from 943 ppm to 1259 ppm.

In the four blooms events, the causative organism was observed forming uniseriate filaments of 21-24 μm wide and trichomes

18-22 μm wide (n = 30), and with a firm yellowish hyaline sheath that surpass trichomes. Cells are shorter than wide and have aerotopes irregularly distributed along the trichome. Trichomes are cylindrical, not constricted at cell walls and with rounded end cells (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Filaments of *Limnoraphis cf. birgei*. Scale bar represents 20 μm.

Initially, the causative species of the blooms was identified as belonging to the genera *Lyngbya* (Quintanilla *et al.*, 2020). However, further literature revision and re-examination of samples has allowed to re-identify the causative organism in the genera *Limnoraphis*. Komárek *et al.* (2013) tentatively identified as *Lyngbya robusta*, recently increased in abundance in Lake Atitlán, Guatemala, and since 2008 annual water-blooms occurred. This was one from the first known cases of *L. robusta* water-blooms worldwide. A polyphasic evaluation of *L. robusta* using 16S rRNA gene sequencing, cytomorphological markers, and ecological characteristics was made. This species had several unique features. It produced aerotopes that were irregularly spaced in cells; cyanotoxins were not found, and it fixed nitrogen in spite of the

lack of heterocytes. It contained a high amount of carotenoids, which caused an unusual brown color of the macroscopic scum on the water level. Molecular phylogenetic analyses using the 16S rRNA gene showed that *L. robusta*, together with few other planktic species, formed a clade, separated from typical *Lyngbya* species. The main diacritical markers of this clade were the planktic type of life and formation of gas vesicles in cells. Based upon molecular, morphological and ecological data, a new genus *Limnoraphis* was proposed with four species. © Czech Phycological Society (2013) proposed the separation of planktonic *Lyngbya* species into the new genera *Limnoraphis* based on a polyphasic classification approach. Currently, there are four species identified within this genera: *Limnoraphis birgei* (G. M. Smith) J. Komárek, E. Zapomelová, J. Smarda, J. Kopecký, E. Rejmánková, J. Woodhouse, B. A. Neilan & J. Komárková 2013, *Limnoraphis criptovaginata* (Schkorbatov) J. Komárek, E. Zapomelová, J. Smarda, J. Kopecký, E. Rejmánková, J. Woodhouse, B. A. Neilan & J. Komárková 2013, *Limnoraphis hieronmuysii* (Lemmermann) J. Komárek, E. Zapomelová, J. Smarda, J. Kopecký, E. Rejmánková, J. Woodhouse, B. A. Neilan & J. Komárková 2013, and *Limnoraphis robusta* (Paracutty) J. Komárek, E. Zapomelová, J. Smarda, J. Kopecký, E. Rejmánková, J. Woodhouse, B. A. Neilan & J. Komárková 2013 (Komárek *et al.*, 2013) tentatively identified as *Lyngbya robusta*, recently increased in abundance in Lake Atitlán, Guatemala, and since 2008 annual water-blooms occurred. This was one from the first known cases of *L. robusta* water-blooms worldwide. A polyphasic evaluation of *L. robusta* using 16S rRNA gene sequencing, cytomorphological markers, and ecological characteristics was made.

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According to the morphological distinction of *Limnoraphis* species made by Komárek *et al.* (2013) tentatively identified as *Lyngbya robusta*, recently increased in abundance in Lake Atitlán, Guatemala, and since 2008 annual water-blooms occurred. This was one from the first known cases of *L. robusta* water-blooms worldwide. A polyphasic evaluation of *L. robusta* using 16S rRNA gene sequencing, cytomorphological markers, and ecological characteristics was made. This species had several unique features. It produced aerotopes that were irregularly spaced in cells; cyanotoxins were not found, and it fixed nitrogen in spite of the lack of heterocytes. It contained a high amount of carotenoids, which caused an unusual brown color of the macroscopic scum on the water level. Molecular phylogenetic analyses using the 16S rRNA gene showed that *L. robusta*, together with few other planktic species, formed a clade, separated from typical *Lyngbya* species. The main diacritical

markers of this clade were the planktic type of life and formation of gas vesicles in cells. Based upon molecular, morphological and ecological data, a new genus *Limnoraphis* was proposed with four species. © Czech Phycological Society (2013, the species found in Lake Coatepeque matches better to the description of *Limnoraphis birgei*; however some feature resemble those of *Limnoraphis robusta*. Filaments' width matches that of *L. birgei* exclusively; however, trichomes width matches with both *L. birgei* and *L. robusta*. It has been identified that *Limnoraphis* trichomes width might decrease during blooms, resembling the morphology of other *Limnoraphis* species (Salazar-Alcaraz *et al.*, 2021), and thus making species identification difficult by means of morphological features alone. As expected, this highlights the need of incorporating molecular and biochemical data in order to confirm the identity of the species found in Lake Coatepeque.

Proliferations of *L. cf. birgei* generated brown surface agglomerations (Fig. 1), which in some cases reached cell concentrations exceeding $900,000 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$. Bloom events were considered as such when there was a noticeable change in water color due to an increase in cyanobacteria cell abundance. During non-bloom conditions, maximum cell abundance was $62,559 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$; while during bloom conditions cell abundance ranged between $168,360$ and $929,280 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$ (Fig. 4).

Filaments were also found in samples from 10 m and 20 m depth but in lower abundances. In some blooms, *Limnoraphis* co-occurred with *Microcystis aeruginosa*. *Limnoraphis* blooms have been scarcely reported in freshwater ecosystems. The reported events have taken

Fig. 4. Cell abundance of *L. cf. birgei* in Lake Coatepeque from May 2018 to December 2020 period.

place at Santa María del Oro crater lake in México (Salazar-Alcaraz *et al.*, 2021), Lake Ontario in Canada (Zastepa and Chemali, 2021), Habanilla reservoir in Cuba (Comas-González *et al.*, 2017), Lake Titicaca in Peru (Komárková *et al.*, 2016), Clear Lake in United States (Kurobe *et al.*, 2013) and Lake Atitlán in Guatemala (Rejmánková *et al.*, 2011).

Blooms of *Limnoraphis* have been related to the upwelling of nutrient rich water (Rejmánková *et al.*, 2011). Particularly, *Limnoraphis robusta* has been reported to occur in oligotrophic to mesotrophic water bodies when phosphorus concentrations increase (Komárek *et al.*, 2013; Salazar-Alcaraz *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, some strains have the ability to fix nitrogen through diazocytes (Rejmánková *et al.*, 2011). Probably this is the case of the *Limnoraphis* strain present in Lake Coatepeque, since it has been confirmed that the lake is oligotrophic.

Further research on the species is needed, both to better understand the potential harm its blooms might represent for the local

inhabitants, as well as to contribute to the morphological and molecular studies of the *Limnorphis* clade.

During blooms events, no human or animal intoxications were reported; however, toxins production needs to be monitored since local population consume the lake's water without any previous treatment, and some species of this genera have been reported to produce trace amounts of cylindrospermopsin and saxitoxins (Rejmánková *et al.*, 2011)

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